

ISic0771

I.Sicily inscription 0771

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic (local)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found in reuse as window sill in house behind chiesa di San Giuseppe sul Castello and given to the museum in 1979

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 17784

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 17.4 cm

Width 69.8 cm

Depth 24.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 43-45 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [Lari]bus Augusteis et Genio Caesa[ris]
2. [Lib]erorumque eius C(aius) Publilius
3. [Phil]argurus sevir primus et prior

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175803

EDR 081546

EDCS 6100296

PHI 334866

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0346a

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 758

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Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 191 no.81 fig.87

Manganaro, Giacomo 1999. Annotazioni sulla epigrafia di Lipara.

Sicilia Epigraphica (Atti del convegno internazionale, Erice, 15-18 ottobre 1998). Pisa. pp. 425-437. At 428

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